

ELECTRICAL ENGINEERING

STUDY OF BEAMS WITH FIBER OPTIC SENSORS USING THE P-125 PRESS

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Abstract

In the article, the author examines the monitoring of the technical condition of extended objects and building structures in real time, which will allow solving a number of important problems related to increasing the efficiency and safety of operation of various buildings and structures.

Keywords: fiber optic sensors, building structures, control methods, optical reflectometer, hardware and software complex.

Introduction. Monitoring the technical condition of extended objects and building structures in real time will allow solving a number of important problems related to increasing the efficiency and safety of operation of various buildings and structures. The sudden destruction of a building structure carries a certain danger and poses a threat to people. Early diagnosis in real time and timely notification of the danger of destruction of a monolithic reinforced concrete building structure, as well as establishing the exact location of crack formation is very relevant.

Materials and methods. The basis of any measuring system based on the use of optical fibers is the following main components: radiation source,

optical fiber, photodetector. The explanatory simplified experimental diagram shown in Figure 1 is based on this principle. Lasers with different wavelengths of 650, 850, 1310, 1550 nm were used in the research. Radiation passes through the optical fiber and falls on the surface of the photodetector. The photodetector converts the light signal into an electrical signal, and then the data processing and output device operates. When mechanically applied to a reinforced concrete beam, deformations occur, which are transmitted to the OM, which in turn causes micro bending. Passing radiation changes its intensity property, the change is recorded by a photodetector.

Figure 1 – Simplified experimental design

The experiment uses a control device, an optical reflectometer Yokogawa AQ1200E type OTDR (Optical Time Domain Reflectometer), manufactured in Japan (Figure 2). This is a multifunctional optical tester designed to measure the parameters of fiber-optic telecommunication lines. This reflectometer provides high accuracy in measuring additional losses within ± 0.05 dB. Like all reflectometers, it has a dead zone of up to 4 meters when measuring additional losses; this is the minimum distance from the optical adapter of the reflectometer to the measurement point. Within the dead zone, the device has a significant error or cannot make measurements at all. The dead zone when measuring the position of an inhomogeneity is already significantly smaller and amounts to 0.8 m. The reflectometer is capable of generating and operating with wavelengths of 1310, 1550, 1625 nm with a deviation of ± 10 nm. This is the deep infrared spectrum, since the APC operates at an optical wavelength of 650 nm, it is

possible to simultaneously transmit two light waves of different lengths, which will not affect each other and disrupt the operation of the FOD. The maximum measurement distance is 500 km, resolution is 0.1 m with a dynamic range of 32 dB. An optical reflectometer makes measurements based on averaging a series of pulses and receiving the reflection of a light wave over a certain period of time; after processing the data, it is built by reflectors. The measurement results are presented in the form of numerical values of instantaneous readings and averaged values on the reflectometer screen using a continuous reflectogram. Introduced additional losses occur on the OF segment at the points of connection and welding, as well as bending. A photograph of the devices discussed above is presented in Figure 2; these devices were used in several experiments as an additional means of controlling additional losses and calibrating the APC.

Figure 2 – Optical reflectometer Yokogawa AQ1200E type OTDR

Materials and methods. To measure additional losses and the level of optical power, two instruments were used: a JDSU SmartPocket OLP-38 optical power meter (made in the USA, former VIAVI trademark) with an absolute change error ± 0.2 dB ($\pm 5\%$) and a range of optical wavelengths from 800 to 1630 nm, the

second device is a radiation source JDSU SmartPocket OLS-35 ((made in the USA, former VIAVI trademark). The generated wavelength of the optical range is from 900 to 1625 nm with a deviation within ± 10 nm.

Figure 3 shows an experiment using a circuit using an APC and an optical reflectometer.

Figure 3 – Photograph of equipment

1 – agro-industrial complex with a personal computer; 2 – optical reflectometer

The processing of the obtained experimental data was carried out taking into account the recommendations of the source [1]. Characteristics of a press with an electromechanical drive brand P-125 were reviewed earlier. Samples of reinforced concrete beams are identical to those previously discussed. When conducting the experiment according to scheme No. 2, 10 beams were destroyed, just like in the experiment performed according to scheme No. 1. Therefore, the description will be presented in abbreviated form, explaining only the essence of the difference between the new version of the scheme (Figure 4). Solid arrows show the movement of the light wave along the optical fiber, dotted arrows show the direction of the reflected part of the light wave, which is captured by the optical reflectometer for analysis. The reflectometer was connected to the FOD using three optical patch cords, each 5 meters long, to eliminate the dead zone.

An optical reflectometer is needed to more accurately determine the location of damage to the beam, which is accepted as a model of a reinforced concrete foundation. The APC is able to determine quite roughly the distance to the site of damage to the foundation,

since it works with a quasi-distributed WOD, while the foundation or an extended object is divided into zones with a length of 5 to 500 meters, so the APC has a resolution limit of 5 meters with a maximum length the foundation is 160 meters, which corresponds to the maximum zone value of 32. If the length of the object is much greater, then the length of the zones will increase to tens or even hundreds of meters.

This agricultural complex is capable of providing control over an area 16 km long with the length of each zone being 500 meters, this is the maximum. Since the ASC and the VOD constitute a single quasi-distributed ASC, if necessary, the number of simultaneously operating ACS can be almost any, and then it is possible to cover large plants with a higher resolution. When using an optical reflectometer and an additional distributed WOD, it is possible to increase the resolution of the APC to 1 meter with a length of the measuring channel of up to 30 km, and with appropriate development of improvements it is possible to reach the level of 0.1 meter at a distance of up to 100 km, which does not go beyond the measurement limits of the reflectometer.

Figure 4 – Scheme

1 – personal computer; 2 – USB cable; 3 – data processing unit; 4- optical adapter; 5 – optical patch cord; 6– VOD; 7 – beam; 8, 9 – supports; 10, 11 – press plates; 12 – direction of application of force; 13 - source with cracks or zone of destruction; 14 – optical reflectometer.

The distributed FOD was connected to an optical reflectometer, as shown in Figure 4, and clearly responded to load changes over a wide range. Since it was located inside the beam, it absorbed all changes in the SSS of the reinforced concrete beam. The screen of the optical reflectometer reflects all changes in the parameters of additional losses due to pressure on the water

supply in real time and in the data averaging mode. When the beam was destroyed, a slight surge and an increase in additional losses were observed, which was recorded on the reflectometer. The scheme fully confirmed its operability and made it possible to determine the location of damage to the reinforced concrete structure using a distributed water sensor.

Figure 5 - The value of losses in OF at a light wavelength of 1550 nm with a step-by-step increase in load

The results of the study are presented in graphs, and data processing was performed using WolframAlpha. A graph of the dependence of the loss values in an optical fiber at a light wavelength of 1550 nm with a stepwise increase in bending pressure is presented in

Figures 60-62. Additional losses are denoted by the symbol A, mechanical stress is denoted by the symbol σ , mechanical deformation is denoted by the symbol ϵ , and load is denoted by the symbol P.

Table 1

Criteria for assessing the quality of automatic approximation

	AIC	BIC	R^2	adjusted R^2
quartic	19.7862	22.1735	0.99945	0.999084
cubic	22.1783	24.1678	0.999127	0.998753
quadratic	36.0178	37.6094	0.996156	0.995194

Conclusion. The materials and methods that were used in carrying out full-scale experiments using lasers with different wavelengths of 650, 850, 1310, 1550 nm are reviewed. The radiation passed through the optical fiber and fell on the surface of the photodetector. The photodetector converted the light signal into an electrical signal, and then the data processing and

output device operated. It was established that mechanical impact on the reinforced concrete beam caused deformations that were transmitted to the OM, which in turn was subjected to microbending. The passing radiation changed its properties and, first of all, its propagation phase and intensity. All changes in the parameters of the light wave were recorded by a photodetector.

Numerical research and data processing were performed using the Wolframalpha and Microsoft Excel programs, which are capable of processing experimental results and constructing approximations of various types, and are also capable of working with data arrays.

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